

EVERSE Industry Survey: Research Software Quality in Commercial Practice

Survey Introduction

Research Software Quality: Bridging Academic and Industry Practice

[EVERSE](#) is a European project developing quality frameworks for research software across research institutions. This survey aims at understanding how commercial organisations approach software quality, particularly when collaborating with research institutions or developing research-adjacent software.

Our framework is built around four key pillars: **Technical Quality** (using ISO standards), **FAIR Principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), **Open Software practices**, and **Sustainability**.

Your participation helps:

- Create common quality standards for research collaborations
- Identify practical research software quality indicators that work in real-world contexts
- Build bridges between academic and commercial software practices

Time commitment: 10-15 minutes

Confidentiality: All responses are anonymous; aggregate findings will be shared with participants

Participation is voluntary and you may withdraw at any time. No personal data is collected unless you opt for follow-up contact.

Section 1: Organisational Context

Q1 Which best describes your organisation's sector?

- Aerospace/defence
- Automotive industries
- Financial services
- Government/public sector

- Manufacturing
- Open source software
- Pharmaceutical/biotech
- Technology consultancy/software development
- Other (please specify): _____

Q2 Does your organisation collaborate with universities or research institutions?

- Regularly (multiple projects per year)
- Occasionally (1-2 projects per year)
- Rarely (less than annually)
- No, but we're considering it
- No, it is not being considered
- We are a research spin-off

Q3 Does your organisation maintain public code repositories (GitHub, GitLab, etc.)? (Select all that apply)

- Yes, extensively - they're important for our technical brand
- Yes, selectively - some projects are open source
- Yes, minimally - mostly documentation/examples
- No, all code is proprietary
- Not sure

Section 2: Software Quality Standards and Practices

Q4 How familiar is your organisation with ISO/IEC 25010 software quality standards?

- Very familiar - we use them regularly in our processes
- Somewhat familiar - we try to use them

- Heard of them but don't actively use them
- Not familiar with these standards

Q5 Select and rank your top 5 most important software quality dimensions. Enter numbers 1-5 next to your chosen items (1 = most important). Leave all other items blank.

- **Functional suitability** - software does what it should do (Rank: ___)
- **Reliability** - works consistently over time without failures (Rank: ___)
- **Performance efficiency** - speed, resource usage, scalability (Rank: ___)
- **Interaction capability** - user experience, interfaces, usability (Rank: ___)
- **Security** - protects information and data appropriately (Rank: ___)
- **Compatibility** - works with other systems and software (Rank: ___)
- **Maintainability** - easy to modify, fix, and understand (Rank: ___)
- **Flexibility** - adapts to changing requirements and environments (Rank: ___)
- **Safety** - avoids danger to people, property, or environment (Rank: ___)

Q6 How do you typically assess software quality? (Select all that apply)

- Code reviews and peer assessment
- Automated testing (unit, integration, system)
- Static code analysis tools
- Performance benchmarking and profiling
- Security scanning and vulnerability assessment
- Compliance audits and certifications
- User acceptance testing
- External quality assessments
- Continuous integration/deployment pipelines
- Software maturity level assessments (e.g., CESSDA Software Maturity Levels)

- FAIR4RS principle evaluation
- Research-specific quality indicators (beyond traditional software metrics)
- Domain-specific compliance frameworks
- We don't have formal quality assessment (*If selected, other assessment options disabled*)
- Other: _____

Section 3: Research Software and Three-Tier Model

Q7 Are you familiar with the term "research software"?

- Very familiar - we develop/work with it regularly
- Somewhat familiar - understand the concept
- Heard the term but unclear on definition
- Not familiar with the term

Q8 EVERSE proposes a "three-tier model" for research software:

- **Analysis code:** Scripts and tools for specific research tasks (data analysis, simulations, one-off experiments)
- **Prototype tools:** Software demonstrating new methods for broader use (proof-of-concept, reusable research tools and services)
- **Research infrastructure:** Established software supporting ongoing research (widely-used libraries, platforms, services)

Does this categorisation make sense for software in your organisation?

- Yes, we have similar categories and this is useful
- Partially - some aspects apply to our work
- No, we categorise software differently
- Not sure - we don't typically categorise research software
- Not applicable - we don't work with research software (*If selected, skip to Q11*)

Q9 If you work with research software, which tier best describes most of your work? (Select all that apply)

- Analysis code (scripts, one-off analysis, experimental work)
- Prototype tools (demonstrating new methods, proof-of-concepts)
- Research infrastructure (established, reusable tools and platforms)
- We don't work with research software (*If selected, skip to Q11*)

Q10 What quality challenges have you observed with research software? (Select all that apply)

- Poor or missing documentation
- Limited or inadequate testing
- Difficult to reproduce results
- Not designed for reuse or extension
- Security vulnerabilities or weak security practices
- Performance issues when scaling up
- Non-standard coding practices
- Lack of version control or change management
- No clear maintenance or support plan
- Difficulty integrating with existing systems
- We haven't observed particular challenges (*If selected, other options disabled*)
- Other: _____

Section 4: FAIR and Open Source Practices

Q11 FAIR4RS principles adapt FAIR data principles for research software's unique characteristics (executable nature, continuous evolution, source code access). How familiar is your organisation with these software-specific adaptations?

- Very familiar - we actively implement FAIR4RS principles

- Somewhat familiar - we understand the concept but implementation is limited
- Familiar with FAIR for data, learning about FAIR4RS for software
- Heard of FAIR4RS but don't understand the differences from FAIR data
- Not familiar with FAIR4RS principles

Q12 How important is open-source software to your organisation?

- Essential - most of our software is open source
- Important - we actively contribute to and use open source
- Useful - we use open source but don't contribute much
- Limited relevance - mostly proprietary software
- Not important - we avoid open source when possible

Section 5: Software Sustainability

Q13 The EVERSE framework emphasises multiple aspects of software sustainability. Which practices does your organisation implement? (Select all that apply)

- Long-term funding or business model planning for software maintenance
- Clear governance processes and community decision-making frameworks
- Regular code refactoring and technical debt management
- Automated testing and continuous integration pipelines
- Community engagement and stakeholder management processes
- Documentation maintenance and knowledge transfer systems
- Performance metrics and project health monitoring
- Succession planning for key developers/maintainers
- Version control and release management
- Dependency management and security updates
- None of these formally implemented (*If selected, other options disabled*)

- Other: _____

Q14 Which research software quality challenges are most significant for your organisation?
(Rank top 3: 1=most significant)

- Ensuring reproducibility across different environments (Rank: ____)
- Balancing speed of research iteration with code quality (Rank: ____)
- Maintaining software beyond the original research project (Rank: ____)
- Managing technical debt in research prototypes (Rank: ____)
- Training researchers in software engineering practices (Rank: ____)
- Coordinating development across distributed research teams (Rank: ____)
- Meeting domain-specific compliance or safety requirements (Rank: ____)
- Demonstrating software impact for research assessment (Rank: ____)

Section 6: Research Software Quality Framework Value

Q15 Would standardised quality frameworks for research software be valuable to your organisation?

- Very valuable - would significantly help our work
- Somewhat valuable - useful for specific projects
- Neutral - might be interesting but not essential
- Not particularly valuable - we have our own standards
- Not sure - would depend on implementation and adoption

Q16 If quality standards for research software existed, how might you use them? (Select all that apply)

- Evaluating potential research collaborations and partnerships
- Setting expectations for university partnerships
- Assessing job candidates' portfolios and experience

- Improving our own research-adjacent code quality
- Contributing to open-source research projects
- Meeting compliance or certification requirements
- Benchmarking against industry best practices
- Evaluating research software sustainability and long-term viability
- Assessing software readiness for community contribution
- Supporting funding applications with quality evidence
- We wouldn't likely use them (*If selected, other options disabled*)
- Other: _____

Q17 EVERSE is developing a "Research Software Quality toolkit ([RSQkit](#))" with curated best practices, tools, and guidance. Would such a resource be useful for your organisation?

- Very useful - we'd actively use and potentially contribute
- Somewhat useful - we'd reference it occasionally
- Potentially useful - depends on quality and implementation
- Not very useful - we have our own established approaches
- Not useful - not relevant to our work

Section 7: Collaboration and Engagement

Q18 Select and rank your top 3 factors that would make you more likely to engage with academic research projects. Enter numbers 1-3 next to your chosen items (1 = most important). Leave others blank.

- Clear software quality standards and expectations (Rank: ____)
- Better project management practices (Rank: ____)
- Clearer intellectual property frameworks (Rank: ____)
- Demonstrated commercial application potential (Rank: ____)
- Access to cutting-edge research and innovation (Rank: ____)

- Talent pipeline and recruitment opportunities (Rank: ____)
- Public relations and brand benefits (Rank: ____)
- Government funding incentives and support (Rank: ____)
- Established software lifecycle management practices (Rank: ____)
- Evidence of sustainable development and maintenance (Rank: ____)
- We already engage regularly with research (*If selected, skip ranking*)
- Other: _____

Q19 Would you be interested in participating in developing quality standards for research software?

- Yes, very interested - we'd like significant input
- Yes, moderately interested - willing to provide feedback
- Maybe - depends on time commitment and relevance
- Probably not - not a current priority
- No - not relevant to our business

Section 8: Follow-up and Contact

Q20 Would you like to be sent the results of this survey?

- Yes
- No

If yes to Q20, please provide your email address: _____

Q21 Would you be interested in participating in a follow-up workshop where we will discuss the findings of this survey?

- Yes
- No

If yes to Q21, please provide your email address: _____

Closing Message

Thank you for contributing to this important research. Your insights will help shape European standards for research software quality and strengthen collaboration between academic and commercial software development.

Survey findings will be available by February 2027. This research will inform the development of the RSQkit (Research Software Quality toolkit) and contribute to building a European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence.

For questions about this research, contact the EVERSE team quoting Industry Survey:
Email: contact@everse.software

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